

Class Management in the Indonesian Language Learning Process for Class V Students at State Primary School 3 Midang Gunungsari West Lombok

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ABSTRACT

Teachers in their role as class managers in learning activities are required to have the abilities and skills so that the expected goals in managing learning activities can be achieved. This is because classroom management in learning activities is an effort made by teachers to create, maintain and develop learning motivation to achieve predetermined goals. Meanwhile, learning itself is the ability to manage operationally and efficiently components related to learning, to produce added value to these components by applicable norms/standards. Classroom management in the learning process which is emphasized in this study is the Indonesian language learning process in Class V of Midang Gunungsari 3 Elementary School, West Lombok with the Big Column (KB) and Big Circle (LB) student seating formations, as well as the obstacles faced by teachers. The results show that when the Indonesian language teacher implements classroom management in the learning process with students sitting in Large Columns (KB) and Large Circles, student learning outcomes average 7.6 grades higher than the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM) score for Indonesian Language subjects (7.5), while the obstacles faced by teachers when implementing classroom management in the learning process by implementing student seating formations, both Large Columns (KB) and Large Circles (LB), originate from teachers and students, who then seek solutions that originate from teachers. Meanwhile, it came from students, 3 students whose learning results were below the KKM score because they did not concentrate when taking part in the lesson and because they often did not go to school, namely through a special approach both when learning took place in the classroom and outside the classroom.

INTRODUCTION

Class management carried out well by teachers is guaranteed to have an impact on the learning process which can achieve the expected goals, both student learning goals and teacher teaching goals. Therefore, teachers are required to have skills based on their ability to be able to design classroom management to support the achievement of learning process objectives which are carried out based on the allocation of available learning time. In the application of classroom management in the learning process, according to Hasibuan and Moejiono (2006) in the *Holistic Journal*, it is "a teacher's skill to create and maintain optimal learning conditions and restore conditions as best as possible if problems occur, either using discipline or carrying out remedial activities for students in the class. Class management can also be said to be an effort made by teachers to create, maintain and develop learning motivation to achieve predetermined goals. Class management in the learning process aims so that every child in the class can work in an orderly manner so that teaching objectives can be achieved effectively and efficiently.

Good classroom management is very necessary for teachers in the learning process because learning itself is "an activity or teaching learning process in which there are two subjects, namely teachers and students". Where "the teacher's position in the learning process is as a subject who is tasked with leading and directing teaching events. Teachers are required to be responsible and take the initiative in delivering learning, while the position of students are people who are directly involved in the learning process teaching. Therefore, they are required to be active." To support the teacher's efforts in managing the class to achieve the learning objectives carried out, the teacher is required to know several things related to class management activities, namely "student management activities, arrangement of learning places, selection of forms of activities, selection of learning media, assessment" as indicators of success. Teachers in creating enabling conditions through classroom management can be seen in an effective teaching and learning process."

Meanwhile, the learning process is one of the school components to increase the quality of learning, apart from the other components. Learning is "the ability to manage operationally and efficiently the components related to learning, to produce added value to these components according to applicable norms/standards. "The components related to schools to improve the quality of learning include teachers, students, school supervisors, facilities/infrastructure, and the learning process."

Meanwhile, Indonesian language learning which is used as a target to determine student learning achievement, is one of several subjects taught at the basic education level. In the context of Indonesian language learning at school, Indonesian language learning "has a central role in the intellectual, social and emotional development of students and is a supporter of success in studying all fields of study. "Language learning is expected to help students get to know themselves, their culture and the cultures of other people, express ideas and feelings, participate in communities that use the language, and discover and use the analytical and imaginative abilities that exist within themselves." Mulyasa in a follow-up statement said that Indonesian language learning is directed at

improving students' ability to communicate in Indonesian well and correctly, both orally and in writing, as well as fostering appreciation for the literary works of Indonesian people. This direction of Indonesian language learning is emphasized in this research, where students can apply Indonesian in communicating every day at school both with teachers and each other. Communication using Indonesian is more directed at verbal communication.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Class Management

a. Understand Classroom Management

Classes as a means used in the implementation of learning by teachers and students will be able to provide benefits in efforts to achieve learning goals when the class is managed well. So, good classroom management becomes the teacher's obligation to organize it. This remembers the definition of classroom management itself, namely "an effort that is deliberately carried out to achieve teaching goals". Class management can also be defined as "efforts made by teaching staff in planning, organizing and optimizing various resources, materials and learning suggestions in the classroom to create effective and quality learning activities for students". In fact, there is also an understanding of classroom management as "the teacher's skill to create and maintain optimal learning conditions and restore them if there is a disruption in the learning process, such as stopping student behavior that diverts class attention, providing rewards for students who are on time in completing assignments or assignments productive group norms". By paying attention to the definition of class management above, it can be stated that class management is a design carried out by the teacher to condition the use of the class according to the chosen format optimally for the realization of an enjoyable learning process so that learning objectives can be achieved.

b. Classroom Management Objectives

Some definitions of classroom management, which is the teacher's ability to create and maintain optimal learning conditions and return them to optimal conditions if disturbances occur, either by disciplining or carrying out remedial activities, then explicitly reflect the goals that are expected when the teacher applies his abilities. These, which in the context of learning are learning objectives. This is because all activities carried out by teachers when carrying out learning lead to achieving learning objectives. In management theory, the aim of classroom management is "to improve the quality of learning. The quality of learning will be achieved if the learning objectives are achieved". Meanwhile, the aim of classroom management is also intended "So that every child in the class can work in an orderly manner so that the teaching objectives can be achieved effectively and efficiently".

Class management objectives are divided into two, namely general objectives and specific objectives. "The general objective of classroom management is to provide and use classroom facilities for various learning and teaching activities in order to achieve good results". Meanwhile, "the specific

aim is to develop students' abilities in using learning tools, provide conditions that enable students to work and study and help students to obtain the expected results".

c. Classroom Management Principles

As a teacher's effort to minimize problems that occur in the classroom, teachers are required to know and master the principles of classroom management and be able to use these principles of classroom management in learning activities. Several principles in management that teachers must know include according to Syaiful Bahri Djamarah and Aswan Zain in Martinis Yamin and Maisah, "warmth and enthusiasm, challenge, variety, flexibility, emphasis on positive things, cultivation of self-discipline". The explanation of each of these classroom management principles is:

- a. The principle of warmth and enthusiasm, where in classroom management a teacher must be able to act intimately with his students and must be enthusiastic about students' tasks and activities in class,
- b. Challenge, where to be able to increasing students' enthusiasm for learning, teachers must be able to pay attention to the use of words, actions, work methods and challenging learning materials,
- c. Flexibility, where to avoid learning boredom in children teachers must be able to vary learning methods, learning tools/media, and interaction patterns with students,
- d. Emphasis on positive things, where as a teacher it would be better if you focus more on students' positive behavior rather than negative behavior,
- e. Instilling self-discipline, where as a teacher you must can encourage students to exercise self-discipline and must also be a role model for students, especially in applying discipline in all things.

d. Activities in Class Management

There are several things that teachers must pay attention to when carrying out classroom management activities, including:

- (1) Physical conditions, where the physical environment of the learning place influences learning outcomes. A physical environment that is favorable and meets minimum requirements supports increasing the intensity of students' learning processes and has a positive influence on achieving learning goals. The physical environment in question includes the room where the teaching and learning process takes place, seating arrangements, ventilation and light arrangements as well as storage arrangements for goods
- (2) Social-emotional conditions, where the social-emotional atmosphere in the classroom has a significant or quite large influence on teaching and learning process, student enthusiasm, effectiveness in achieving teaching goals. Social-emotional conditions in classroom management consist of:

- Leadership type, where the teacher's leadership type colors the emotional atmosphere in the classroom. A type of leadership that is heavier on authoritarianism will produce a submissive or apathetic student attitude. On the other hand, it will also foster an aggressive attitude
 - The teacher's attitude, where the teacher's attitude in dealing with students who violate school rules should remain patient, and remain friendly with a belief that the student's behavior will be corrected
 - Voice teacher, where the teacher's voice, although not a big factor, also influences learning. A voice that is high-pitched or always high or so low that students cannot hear it clearly from a distance will be boring and the lesson will not be paid attention to. This kind of atmosphere contains undesirable behavior
 - Fostering working relationships, namely fostering good relationships between teachers and students in classroom management matters is very important. With a good relationship between teachers and students, it is hoped that students will always be happy, full of passion and enthusiasm, optimistic and realistic in the learning activities that are being carried out
- (3) Organizational conditions, where routine activities carried out organizationally both at the class level and at the school level will be able to prevent class management problems. Routine activities that have been clearly regulated and communicated openly to all students will result in the instillation of good habits and regular behavior in each student. These activities include:
- Changing lessons
 - Teachers being unable to attend
 - Problems between students
 - Flag ceremonies
 - Other activities

e. Approaches to Classroom Management

Approaches that can be applied by teachers in classroom management include the "Authority approach, intimidation approach, permissive approach, cookbook approach, instructional approach, behavior change approach, socio-emotional climate approach, group process approach, eclectic approach, and pluralistic analytical approach".

The ten approaches that can be applied by teachers as stated above, if described above, are as follows:

- (1) Authority approach, namely controlling student behavior by teachers, by enforcing rules, giving orders, directions and messages, using reprimands, using control with take an approach, using separation and exclusion.

- (2) The intimidation approach is controlling student behavior using forms of intimidation. The teacher forces students to behave according to the teacher's orders.
- (3) A permissive approach is controlling student behavior with an approach that emphasizes giving students freedom. The teacher acts as a driving force to develop students' potential.
- (4) The cookbook approach is controlling students' behavior in the form of recommendations about things that must be done or cannot be done.
- (5) The instructional approach is an approach to controlling behavior by creating effective learning, so as to minimize disruption to the implementation of learning.
- (6) The behavior change approach is behavior control which emphasizes positive reinforcement, punishment, termination, and negative reinforcement for changes in behavior caused by the results of the teaching and learning process.
- (7) The socio-emotional climate approach is a control approach behavior on positive relationships between teachers and students.
- (8) The group process approach is controlling behavior using a class group approach as a social system that supports the creation of a learning atmosphere in the classroom.
- (9) The eclectic approach is controlling student behavior by combining various approaches that is possible.
- (10) A pluralistic analytical approach is an approach to student behavior with an approach that looks at the plurality of classroom conditions faced.

f. Problems in Classroom Management

Classroom management, as stated above, is a teacher's skill in creating and maintaining learning conditions, so in implementing these skills there are of course obstacles that can disrupt students' conditions in participating in learning. Therefore, teachers as class managers are required to take action to prepare optimal learning conditions so that the learning process can take place effectively. This is in line with the aim of classroom management, namely so that every child in the class can work in an orderly manner so that teaching objectives are achieved effectively and efficiently. Paying attention to the meaning and objectives of classroom management as stated above, it is necessary to understand the group's understanding of the problems of classroom management itself, which include individual problems and group problems.

Individual problems, where this problem arise because in individuals there is a need to be accepted by the group and to achieve self-esteem. If an individual's needs cannot be met through good means, then the individual concerned will look for other ways to achieve their needs by doing bad things. Roestiyah NK distinguishes four groups of individual classroom management problems which are based on the assumption that all individual behavior is an

effort to achieve the goal of fulfilling the decision to be accepted by the group and the need to achieve self-esteem. If these needs can no longer be met through common and acceptable means by society, in this case, class society, then the individual concerned will try to achieve them by other means. In other words, he will do bad things. Actions to achieve goals in an asocial way are classified into "(1) Behavior that wants to get other people's attention (attention-getting behaviors), for example clowning in class (active), or by acting slowly so that you need extra help (passive), (2) Behavior that wants to show power (power seeking behaviors). For example, always arguing or losing emotional control, getting angry, crying (active), or always "forgetting" important rules in class (passive), (3) Behavior that aims to hurt other people (revenge-seeking behaviors), for example hurting other people like calling, hitting, biting and so on (This group is mostly in active/passive form), and (4) Demonstration of inability, namely in the form of completely refusing to try to do anything because they believe that only failure is part of it".

Group problems, where group problems in classroom management according to Johnsons and Bany, in Asmawati, are: "(1) Lack of unity, characterized by conflicts between individuals and sub-groups, (2) A tendency for disruption, work congestion and manufactured behavior create, and (3) Low fighting spirit and hostile attitudes". Meanwhile, according to Lois V Johnsons and Mary A Bany in Roestyah, NK, put forward 6 categories of group problems in classroom management, namely "(1) The class is less cohesive, for example, differences in gender, ethnicity and socio-economic level, and so on, (2) The class reacts negatively to one of its members, for example mocking a class member who is teaching voice art, singing out of tune, (3) "Encouraging" class members who violate group norms, for example encouraging the class clown, (4) The group tends to easily distract from the task at hand, (5) Low morale, for example, a protest action against the teacher because they consider the task given to be unfair, and (6) The class is less able to adapt to new circumstances, for example, schedule disruptions, or the class teacher forced to be replaced temporarily by another teacher and so on".

Paying close attention to the problems faced by teachers in classroom management, whether related to individual problems or group problems, can gain an understanding that these problems occur because they involve the emotional state of students who want special attention from the teacher who teaches and from other students.

g. Factors Influencing Classroom Management

Factors that influence classroom management which basically consist of:

- (1) Teacher factors, which consist of the type of teacher leadership, monotonous teaching and learning format, teacher personality, teacher knowledge, and teacher understanding of students,
- (2) Student/student factors,
- (3) Family factors
- (4) Facility factors, which consist of

- The number of students in the class, where when the number of students is large it is certainly difficult to manage
- Large classrooms, when small classrooms and not proportional to the number of students and the need for students to move around the class is another obstacle to classroom management
- The number of rooms is less than the needs and the number of special rooms needed such as laboratories, auditoriums, art rooms, drawing rooms, sports rooms, and so on require separate handling, and an insufficient number of books or other tools that do not match the number of students who need them will cause classroom management problems”

The demand for teachers to know several things related to classroom management as stated above is to increase the role of teachers in the teaching and learning process and student learning outcomes as stated by Purnomo (2017) in the *Innovative Journal (Journal of Social Science Research)*, teachers must hope to be able to create and maintain an effective learning environment and be able to manage the classroom well because the classroom is a learning environment and is an aspect of the school environment that needs to be organized. This environment needs to be regulated and supervised so that learning activities are directed towards educational goals, teachers must be able to motivate students to be active in learning. In the learning process, classroom management is also all of the teacher's efforts and actions to foster and use classroom resources optimally, selectively and effectively to create conditions or resolve classroom problems so that the teaching and learning process can run smoothly.

2. Learning Process

a. Understanding Learning

Learning is an interaction between teachers and students at school to achieve learning goals that have been set based on the material taught. Several learning components must be implemented by teachers when learning takes place from a single unit where each component is interconnected with the other. These learning components include objective components, material components, method components, media components and evaluation components. Learning in theoretical terms means. Teaching students using educational principles and learning theories which are the main determinants of educational success. Learning is a two-way communication process, teaching is carried out by the teacher as an educator while learning is carried out by the students or students. Learning is also defined as "The ability to manage operationally and efficiently the components related to learning, thereby producing added value to these components according to applicable norms/standards. The components related to schools to improve the quality of learning include teachers, students, school supervisors, facilities/infrastructure, and the learning process”. The success of teaching and learning activities carried out by teachers in the classroom is demonstrated by the teaching and learning results obtained after the learning takes place. The results obtained through learning activities are student learning outcomes and

teacher teaching outcomes. In its definition, learning outcomes are "changes in behavior in students which can be measured in the form of changes in knowledge, attitudes and skills. This change can be interpreted as an improvement and development that is better than before". Bloom in Agus Suprijono stated that "Learning outcomes include cognitive, affective and psychomotor abilities". Learning outcomes are also abilities obtained by individuals after the learning process takes place, which can provide changes in behavior, including knowledge, understanding, attitudes and skills of students so that they become better than before".

b. Learning Components

Learning as an activity carried out by teachers when interacting with students in the classroom has several components that teachers must pay attention to when learning takes place. Various views have emerged in providing concepts about learning components. Martinis Yamin and Maisah expressed their views on the components of learning, namely "students, teachers, curriculum, facilities and infrastructure, school management, learning process management, fund management, monitoring and partnerships". The explanation of each learning component is:

- (1) Students, including socio-economic, cultural and geographic environment/environment, intelligence, personality, talents and interests,
- (2) Teachers, including educational background, work experience, teaching load, conditions economics, work motivation, commitment to tasks, discipline and creativity,
- (3) Curriculum, which includes objectives, materials, methods and evaluation,
- (4) Educational facilities and infrastructure, including teaching aids/practical equipment, laboratory, library, skills room, counseling guidance room, UKS room and multi-purpose room,
- (5) School management, including classroom management, teacher management, student management, facilities and infrastructure, improving order/discipline, and leadership,
- (6) Learning process management including teacher appearance, mastery of material/curriculum, use of learning methods/strategies, and utilization of learning facilities,
- (7) Fund management, including budget planning (RAPBS), sources of funds, use of funds, reports and supervision,
- (8) Monitoring and evaluation, including the school principal as supervisors at their schools, school supervisors, and school committee members who are also supervisors, as well as
- (9) Partnerships, including school relations with government agencies, relations with the business world and community leaders, and other educational institutions.

The description of the learning components above provides a more perfect understanding for teachers that it is not only the objectives, materials,

methods, media, and evaluation as well as the teaching and learning process that are components of learning but also teachers and students, curriculum and infrastructure, good management of learning process management, school management and fund management, as well as partnerships and monitoring.

c. Student Seating Arrangements during Learning

One thing that teachers must also pay attention to when managing the classroom during learning activities is the arrangement of students' seating during the lesson. The activity of arranging students' seats when taking part in learning is important because arranging students' seating in the classroom allows for comprehensive face-to-face contact so that teachers can control student behavior. Student seating arrangements can influence the smoothness of the teaching and learning process, as stated by Wiyani seating arrangements are "one of the efforts made by teachers in managing the class because an effective class will determine the learning outcomes achieved. "With good seating arrangements, it is hoped that learning conditions will be created that are conducive and also enjoyable for students". Winzer in Winataputra, states that "seating arrangements are the appropriate arrangement of the classroom environment which influences the level of student involvement and participation in the learning process. Furthermore, it is known that where students sit affects the time students use to complete the assigned tasks". The teacher as a class manager can arrange seating in various positions, and to be able to innovate in student seating arrangements in the classroom, the teacher must know the various seating arrangement formations. Several student seating formations in the classroom are used as references by teachers when arranging student seating, including "Large Column (KB), Large Circle (LB), Letter U Formation, Team Pattern Formation, Conference Table, Traditional Class, and Auditorium of the five student seating formations in the classroom, two of them were studied in this research related to classroom management in learning activities, namely the Large Column (KB) student seating formation and the Large Circle (LB) student seating formation.

METHODOLOGY

To find data on classroom management in the Indonesian language learning process in Class V of the 3 Midang Gunungsari Elementary School, West Lombok, the research approach applied is qualitative research, which is "A research method used to examine the condition of natural objects, where the researcher is as a key instrument, the data collection technique is carried out in a triangulated (combined) manner, data analysis is inductive, and the results of qualitative research emphasize meaning rather than generalization, with data collection methods being interviews, observation and documentation. The interview method is "A conversation with a specific purpose, the conversation is carried out by two parties, namely the interviewer who asks questions and the interviewee who provides answers to those questions", where in data collection efforts one of the two is applied. The type of interview is an unstructured interview. This type of interview is more informal, questions about the subject's outlook on life, attitudes, beliefs, or other information can be

asked freely to the subject. Interviews like this are broad and usually planned to suit the subject and atmosphere at the time the interview is conducted. Then the observation method is also applied, which is "A data collection technique by observing every event that is taking place and recording it with an observation tool about the things that will be observed or researched", where in data collection one of two types of observation is applied namely indirect observation and/or non-participants.

The interview and observation methods applied in data collection were intended to obtain data about the implementation of class management activities in the Indonesian Language learning process for Class VA students, the obstacles faced by teachers when implementing class management in the Indonesian Language learning process for Class VA students, and the efforts made by teachers in overcoming the obstacles faced when implementing class management in the Indonesian language learning process for Class VA students at State Elementary School 3 Midang Gunungsari West Lombok Academic Year 2023/2024. To obtain data that can be verified as true, data analysis is carried out by applying inductive data analysis which is "an analysis based on the data obtained, then developing certain relationship patterns or making hypotheses". This data analysis is applied to find data that is specific so that these specific characteristics can then be generalized into general properties. There are three steps taken in analyzing data as stated in the theory

- (1) Data reduction, namely summarizing, selecting the main things, focusing on the important things, looking for themes and main points and discarding what is not necessary. In this way, the data that has been reduced will provide a clearer picture, and make it easier for researchers to carry out further data collection, and search for it if necessary,
- (2) Data presentation (data display) is carried out after the data has been reduced, where the data presentation can be done in the form of a short description, charts, relationships between categories and the like,
- (3) Drawing conclusions and verification (conclusion drawing and verification), where the initial conclusions put forward are still temporary, and will change if strong supporting evidence is not found at the next stage of data collection.

However, if the conclusions put forward at the initial stage are supported by valid and consistent evidence when the researcher returns to the field to collect data, then the conclusions put forward are credible." Meanwhile, the validity of the data applied is:

- (1) Persistence or regularity of observation which is "consistently seeking interpretations in various ways with a constant and tentative analysis process. Diligence in observation means "finding characteristics and elements in a situation that are very relevant to the problem or issue being sought and then focusing on these things in detail,
- (2) Triangulation, which is a data validity checking technique that utilizes something else.

The most widely used triangulation technique is examination through other sources. Denzin (1978) in Lexy J. Moleong, distinguishes four types of triangulation as examination techniques that can be utilized, namely "Use of sources, methods, investigators, and theory. The triangulation used is source triangulation in addition to method triangulation and data triangulation. Because researchers compare and check the degree of trustworthiness of information obtained through different times and tools in qualitative research. When this activity is carried out, it can be achieved by comparing observational data with interview data, comparing what people say in public with what they say in private, comparing what people say about the research situation with what they say". All the time, comparing a person's situation and perspective with various opinions and views of people such as ordinary people, people with middle or high education, wealthy people, government people, and comparing the results of interviews with the contents of related documents".

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Meanwhile, the validity of the data applied is:

- (1) Persistence or regularity of observation which is "consistently seeking interpretations in various ways with a constant and tentative analysis process. Diligence in observation means "finding characteristics and elements in a situation that are very relevant to the problem or issue being sought and then focusing on these things in detail,
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Tabel 1. Large Column (KB) and Large Circle (LB)

No	Large Column (KB)	Mark	%	Great Circle (LB)	Mark	%
1.	2 persons	7,2	8,3	1 person	7,2	4,2
2.	1 person	7,3	4,2	1 person	7,3	4,2
3.	6 people	7,5	25	4 people	7,5	16,7

4.	2 persons	7,6	8,3	3 people	7,6	12,5
5.	2 Persons	7,7	8,3	3 people	7,7	12,5
6.	1 person	7,8	4,2	1 person	7,8	4,2
7.	1 person	8,2	4,2	1 person	8,2	4,2
8.	1 person	8,3	4,2	1 person	8,3	4,2
9.	8 people	8,5	33,3	8 people	8,5	33,3

Regarding the obstacles faced by teachers when managing classrooms in learning activities using the Large Column (KB) and Large Circle (LB) student seating formats, these are caused by two factors, namely factors originating from within the teacher himself and factors originating from the students. These two obstacle factors are in line with Purnomo's statement, namely "There are two factors that influence learning, namely factors that exist within oneself or individual factors, and factors that exist outside the individual or social factors". The factors that exist within oneself or individual factors in this case are from the teacher which is basically because the Indonesian language teacher is not used to implementing the two student sitting formations when learning in the classroom. This is because before implementing these two student seating formations the teacher sat more in a chair when explaining the learning material being taught, while when implementing these two student seating formations the teacher was required to stand more than sitting in a chair when carrying out learning, this is done so that teachers can easily control students in the classroom and can easily approach each student's seat, both when students sit in rows from right to left when implementing the Large Column (KB) student sitting formation or when the students sit in a circle in a circle. teacher sitting or Big Circle (LB) formation.

Meanwhile, factors outside the individual, in this case, are students, where there were 3 students when implementing the Large Column (KB) student sitting formation and 2 students when implementing the Large Circle (LB) student seating formation, the main cause of which was the students' lack of concentration in participating in the lesson. or students do more other activities such as chatting with their friends when the teacher explains learning material, are less serious in carrying out the tasks given by the teacher, and likewise lack concentration when the teacher provides guidance. Paying attention to the two opinions above, shows clearly the connection between the obstacles faced by Indonesian language teachers in implementing classroom management in the learning process, both by implementing the Large Column (KB) and Large Circle (LB) student seating formations which originate from two causal factors, namely the teacher and According to Purnomo, factors from teachers are included in external factors in the school factors section, one of which is the teacher's relationship with students, while factors originating from

students are internal factors which are included in psychological factors, one of which is students' concerns and interests.

As a teacher who hopes that classroom management learning will get optimal results or achieve learning goals or the teacher's teaching goals and students' learning goals, then efforts are made to overcome the two obstacles faced as stated above. When facing obstacles that originate from the teacher, the efforts made are to always try so that every time learning takes place the teacher stands more in front of the class and approaches each student's seat when implementing the Large Column (KB) student sitting formation, and likewise when implementing Large Circle (KB) student seating formation. Or it can be stated that the teacher's presence is when learning in the classroom involves more standing than sitting in the chairs provided in the classroom. Meanwhile, when facing obstacles originating from students, efforts are made by always approaching the five students who experience failure in participating in learning, both when implementing the Large Column (KB) and Large Circle (LB) sitting formations and providing motivation to always take the learning seriously, also by providing guidance and education to them when outside the classroom by calling them to the teacher's room to be given advice and guidance.

The efforts made by teachers to overcome obstacles when managing learning activities as stated above, are part of efforts to strengthen self-competence which in Law Number 14 of 2005 concerning teachers and lecturers in Chapter IV Article 10 states that three competencies must be implemented. teachers possess in learning activities, namely "pedagogical competence, personality competence, social competence and professional competence". Meanwhile, the efforts made by Indonesian language teachers in overcoming obstacles when implementing classroom management in learning process activities both by implementing the Large Column (KB) and Large Circle (LB) student seating formations as stated above, which originate from students are (1) reviewing the status (status assessment), which is the stage of identifying the nature and extent of learning difficulties faced by students. Steps that can be applied in assessing the status of students' learning difficulties include (a) what specific goals are expected to be achieved by the student concerned when learning difficulties appear? (b) which techniques can be used to determine the extent to which students did the student concerned to achieve this goal (at the beginning?) (c) after the assessment technique was used, what pattern of differences existed between what was expected and the actual actions of the student concerned? (summary of the strengths and weaknesses in the pattern), (2) cue estimation, which is the stage of estimating the reasons or causes underlying the pattern of learning outcomes shown by the student concerned. Steps that can be taken in estimating the causes of student learning difficulties (a) Which appropriate reasons that cause student learning difficulties are used in stage one? (b) how can teachers assess and determine the reasons at the initial stage, which is the most appropriate and strong? (c) after applying the assessment techniques listed in the second step, a conclusion can be drawn as to what are the strong factors causing the learning difficulties experienced by

students? (3) problem solving and assessment (treatment and treatment evaluation), is a stage to eliminate causes of learning difficulties faced by students. Steps that can be taken are (a) choosing which techniques should be used to help with the learning difficulties experienced by students? and (b) which assessment techniques can be used to determine the extent of success in solving the learning difficulties experienced by students. and knowing what the results are. assessment carried out to solve the student's learning difficulties, should it continue or should it be changed to another technique?

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this section, conclusions are presented based on the previous discussion, where the conclusions are as follows:

1. Implementation of class management in the learning process in Class VA of Midang Gunungsari State Elementary School 3, West Lombok, Academic Year 2023/2024 is implemented using the Large Column (KB) and Large Circle (LB) student seating format with learning outcomes obtained based on average grades. The average class score for the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM) for Indonesian language subjects (7.5) is 7.6, where a score of 7.6 is higher than a score of 7.5 or $7.6 > 7.5$. The obstacles faced by Indonesian language teachers in implementing class management in the Indonesian language learning process in Class VA of State Elementary School 3 Midang Gunungsari West Lombok for the 2023/2024 academic year through the implementation of the Large Column (KB) and Large Circle (LB) student seating formations are sourced from teachers and students where obstacles originate from teachers (internal) because teachers are not used to implementing learning with both types of student seating formations, and obstacles originating from students (external) are caused by students' lack of concentration when taking part in learning and often not attending school, especially those that occur on 5 students.
2. Efforts made by teachers in dealing with obstacles when implementing class management in Indonesian language learning activities in Class VA of Midang Gunungsari State Elementary School 3, West Lombok, Academic Year 2023/2024, which originate from teachers who always try to stand more during learning compared to sitting in a chair. The obstacles originate from students always paying attention to the 5 students who experience problems when participating in learning and approaching them when they don't pay attention to the teacher's explanations, asking them to be serious when given assignments and when being guided.

FURTHER RESEARCH

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "Class Management in the Indonesian Language Learning Process for Class V Students at State Primary School 3 Midang Gunungsari West Lombok".

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